

THE PRACTICE OF APPLYING LEAN EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: *The paper presents options for using lean teaching methods in the practice of higher education institutions in the digital economy. Taking into account the transition from traditional to electronic education, the main directions for realizing the possibilities of lean methodology are highlighted.*

Key words: *e-education, lean learning, methods, waste, culture of continuous improvement.*

In modern conditions of development of digital education, the use of innovative strategies and solutions to increase the competitiveness of higher educational institutions, which includes lean learning, is becoming a relevant area. Taking into account the transition from traditional to electronic education, the main directions for implementing the capabilities of lean methodology are highlighted. It is believed that they can improve students' learning and optimize administrative processes. I.A. Volkova presented the results of the answers to her question "Is it possible to apply the principles of lean production in the practice of modern educational organizations?", noting a positive assessment of this prospect by the majority of respondents (96.6%), and also identifying areas for the application of lean: "— to improve educational processes, optimize work; — to increase the efficiency of the educational organization; — to improve the quality of education; — in order to reduce time and financial losses"[1]

Presently, there is no clear understanding of this concept, at the same time, the factor of "lean consciousness", whose bearer is a specific person (head of an educational organization, teacher, mentor), is given special attention in works reflecting the problems of introducing lean technologies. [2] Therefore, the success of the entire educational organization, the achievement of strategic development goals that determine the quality of our national education system depends on the level of maturity, conscientiousness and economical consciousness of each subject of educational relations.[3]

Lean learning focuses on maximizing value while minimizing waste, and is effectively applied to e-learning in several ways:

1. Continuous improvement. Lean manufacturing emphasizes a culture of continuous improvement (Kaizen). In e-learning, this may include regular evaluation

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of course content, course delivery methods, and student feedback to improve the quality of learning.

2. Value stream mapping. By mapping the e-Learning process—from course design to delivery—educators can identify bottlenecks or inefficiencies, allowing them to streamline processes and improve outcomes.

3. Student-centered approach. Lean methodologies promote a focus on what is of value to the student. This means designing courses that meet the needs and preferences of students, ensuring efficient allocation of resources.

4. Rapid prototyping. When developing e-Learning courses, using rapid prototyping can help instructors quickly test and refine course materials based on student feedback before full-scale implementation.

5. Elimination of losses. Lean principles can help identify and eliminate unnecessary practices in e-Learning, such as unnecessary content or redundant assessments, ensuring that every element of the course adds value.

Educational institutions that practice lean education have significant economic benefits, both direct and indirect.[4] These effects include:

1. Cost reduction
2. Improved performance
3. Higher enrollment and retention rates
4. Increase in income
5. Long-term sustainability
6. Stakeholder satisfaction

Along with the benefits of implementing lean teaching in higher education institutions, there are a number of losses noted by students: inconvenient location of university equipment, uneven distribution of taught subjects throughout the day and semester, lack of understanding of the curriculum, inadequate communication between teachers and students, and improper management of university facilities. [5] In general, the following losses can be determined for an educational institution:

1. Costs of personnel training;
2. Resistance to change on the part of teachers and students;
3. Technical costs;
4. Temporary losses;
5. Short-term results; [6]
6. Unforeseen risks.

Lean training lays the foundation for lean thinking with which a specialist comes to his future place of work. If you start implementing lean learning from school and continue at all stages of education, a person will not be able to work differently: he will see losses and be intransigent towards them. Underestimating the potential of lean learning is detrimental to the economy of any country.[7] The economic implications

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of implementing lean methodology in higher education are multifaceted and impact operational costs, productivity, revenue generation and long-term sustainability. By fostering a culture of continuous improvement, higher education institutions can not only improve their financial performance, but also improve the quality of education they provide, ultimately benefiting students, faculty, and the broader community.

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(3rd international scientific and practical conference)